

IN-SITU THERMAL STRESS MEASUREMENT OF TUNGSTEN FIBER REINFORCED TITANIUM COMPOSITE BY HIGH-LOW TEMPERATURE X-RAY DIFFRACTION

Masayuki Nishida¹, Taisei Doi², Tatsuya Matsue³ and Takao Hanabusa⁴

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kobe City College of Technology
8-3, Gakuenhigashi-machi, Nishi-ku, Kobe, Hyogo 651-2194, Jpapr
Email: nishida@kobe-kosen.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.kobe-kosen.ac.jp>

² Advanced Course Student of Mechanical Engineering, Kobe City College of Technology,
8-3, Gakuenhigashi-machi, Nishi-ku, Kobe, Hyogo 651-2194, Jpapr
Email: r109182@g.kobe-kosen.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.kobe-kosen.ac.jp>

³ Department of Environmental Materials Engineering,
Niihama National College of Technology,
7-1, Yakumo-cho, Niihama, Ehime 792-8580, Japan
Email: tmatsue@mat.niihama-nct.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.niihama-nct.ac.jp>

⁴ The University Tokushima,
2-1, Minamijosanjima-cho, Tokushima 770-8506, Japan
Email: hanabusa.takao@tokushima-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.tokushima-u.ac.jp/e/>

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ABSTRACT

The tungsten fiber reinforced titanium composite (W/Ti composite) was produced by the spot welding method. This manufacturing method used only a simple spot welding system, and it did not need a vacuum chamber and a high temperature furnace such as existing common methods. The thermal residual stress alteration of W/Ti composite was estimated by the x-ray diffraction with the cryogenic cooling system. Residual stress alterations were measured by the in-situ x-ray stress measurement technique under the cooling cycles from 25°C to -250 °C. Residual stresses in tungsten-fiber were investigated at several temperatures. In the longitudinal fiber direction, the initial thermal residual stress generated in the manufacturing process was -810MPa. These thermal residual stresses change to the maximum value of -1000MPa in the lowest temperature at -250°C. It is assumed that these results depend on the thermal expansion mismatch between the titanium-matrix and the tungsten-fiber. The calculated results of the simple elastic model consisting of the thermal expansion mismatch and the volume fraction agreed with the experimental results of in-situ thermal stress measurement qualitatively. Furthermore, these results of the thermal stress alteration were discussed with the other results in the high temperature state which has been reported same author.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced materials have found considerable application in the improvement of the performance characteristics of engineering materials. Commonly, there is a large difference in thermal expansion coefficients between the matrix and the fiber. This mismatch causes the thermo-reduce residual stresses in every composite system [1,2]. These thermal residual stresses are big problems which can never be avoided.

On the other hand, the effective method has been made on analyzing the thermal stress on the surface of composite materials by the x-ray stress measurement technique [2,3]. This method is essentially based on the $\sin^2\psi$ method [4].

In this study, the tungsten fiber reinforced titanium composite (W/Ti) was prepared to investigate the thermal residual stresses. This W/Ti composite consisted of the continuous tungsten fiber and the

pure titanium matrix. This W/Ti composite was produced by the simply spot welding method. Furthermore, thermal residual stresses in the composite were examined by the in-situ x-ray stress measurement method. The in-situ stress measurement under several low temperature states was performed. Stress alterations during cryogenic cycling were estimated by the combination of the x-ray diffraction and the cryogenic cooling systems. Temperature was changed from 25°C to -250°C periodically, and thermal stresses in the tungsten fiber were measured at each temperature.

2 PREPARATION OF FIBER REINFORCED MATERIAL [5]

The W/Ti composite was produced for the present investigation by the unique method. The W/Ti composite consisted of two components, 99.99% purity tungsten fiber with 100 μ m diameter and 99.9% industrial purity titanium plate of thickness 0.5mm or 0.2mm. These were used for the fiber phase and the matrix phase, respectively. The W/Ti composite was produced by the spot welding machine. This manufacturing method used only a simple spot welding machine system, and it did not need a vacuum chamber and a high temperature furnace such as existing common methods. The tungsten fiber was twisted regularly on the titanium plate of the thickness 0.5mm. This titanium plate twisted the tungsten fiber was sandwiched between other titanium plates of the thickness 0.2mm. After depositing seven layers, these were fixed by the spot welding. However this method has a problem, this W/Ti composite did not joint in the whole position between the tungsten fiber and the titanium matrix because of the partial welding in the spot welding point. Therefore, the jointing of the spot welding should be repeated on a number of times. The coverage, a rate of welding area to the whole plate area, became in 150% for the sample in this producing, because it should make up for the partial welding by this method.

Figure 1(a) shows the schematic diagram of the manufacturing method for the W/Ti composite by the spot welding. Fig. 1(b) shows the spot welding positions which define the coverage for W/Ti composite. The coverage became 150% for this sample in Fig. 1(b).

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of: (a) the manufacturing procedure by the spot welding method, (b) the spot welding positions which define the coverage for the W/Ti composite.

Figure 2 (a) and (b) show the photographs of the W/Ti composite. Fig. 2(a) is the microphotograph of the cross section of W/Ti composite. The distance between the arranged lines of tungsten fibers is about 0.5mm and 0.2mm which depends on the thickness of the titanium plate. Fig.2(b) is the specimen surface for the x-ray stress measurement. The conditions of the spot welding are shown in Table 1. After the spot welding, the surface of the sample was polished with #2000 emery paper in

order to strip off the indentations of the spot welding. Therefore, the surface of the W/Ti sample has residual stresses caused by the emery polishing. This sample was annealed at 630°C for 2 hours to cancel the surface residual stresses which were generated by the emery polishing. After annealing treatment, this W/Ti composite were estimated by the x-ray stress measurement technique. The final dimension of the sample for the in-situ thermal residual stress measurement was 15mm × 15mm, thickness 5mm. The volume fraction of the tungsten fiber is about 5 % in this sample.

Figure 2: Photographs of the W/Ti composite; (a) a microphotograph of the cross section of the W/Ti composite, (b) the specimen surface polished by emery paper #2000 for the x-ray stress measurement.

Welding voltage [V] & current [A]	200, 8.5
Welding pressure [kN]	1.9
Holding time [msec.]	200
Diameter of electrode [mm]	11

Table 1: Conditions of spot welding.

3 THEORY OF X-RAY STRESS MEASUREMENT [4]

The long-fiber reinforced composite considered in this investigation is schematically shown in Fig.3. The x_1 and x_2 axes are parallel to and the x_3 axis is normal to the specimen surface, with the x_1 axis being defined as parallel to the fiber direction.

Figure 3: Coordinate system and definition of the ψ and ϕ angles.

The normal lattice strain $\epsilon_{\phi\psi}$ of a particular hkl plane defined by the angles ϕ and ψ is also shown in this figure. According to the theory of isotropic elasticity, the strain $\epsilon_{\phi\psi}$ is given by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{\phi\psi} = & \frac{1+\nu}{E} (\sigma_{11} \cos^2 \phi + \sigma_{12} \sin 2\phi + \sigma_{22} \sin^2 \phi - \sigma_{33}) \sin^2 \psi \\ & + \frac{1+\nu}{E} \sigma_{33} - \frac{\nu}{E} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + \frac{1+\nu}{E} (\sigma_{23} \sin \phi + \sigma_{31} \cos \phi) \sin 2\psi, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio. To consider the longitudinal stress σ_{11} parallel to the fibers, we define the angle ϕ equals zero. It was previously reported that both the stresses parallel normal to the fiber are principal stresses and no shearing stress exists[2]. If the plane stress condition is maintained in the surface layer, we can assume the stress $\sigma_3=0$, Therefore, the Eq. (1) is transformed into Eq. (2) for $\phi=0^\circ$.

$$\varepsilon_{\psi} = \frac{1+\nu}{E} \sigma_1 \sin^2 \psi - \frac{\nu}{E} (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2). \quad (2)$$

From this equation, it means that the relationship of ε_{ψ} vs. $\sin^2 \psi$ is linear, and the longitudinal stress σ_1 is determined from the slope of the ε_{ψ} - $\sin^2 \psi$ diagram. Therefore, the $\sin^2 \psi$ method can be used for the estimation of the stress condition in surface region. Furthermore, when ε_{ψ} is calculated from the diffraction angle $2\theta_{\psi}$,

$$\varepsilon_{\psi} = \frac{d_{\psi} - d_0}{d_0} = -(\theta_{\psi} - \theta_0) \cot \theta_0 \cdot \frac{\pi}{180}, \quad (3)$$

where θ_0 (degrees) is the diffraction angle of the stress free state. The 2θ - $\sin^2 \psi$ diagram can be obtained by measuring 2θ at several values of ψ angles. By substituting Eq.(3) into Eq.(2), we obtain the following.

$$\sigma_1 = -\frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \cot \theta_0 \frac{\partial(2\theta_{\psi})}{\partial(\sin^2 \psi)} \cdot \frac{\pi}{180}. \quad (4)$$

The gradient of the regression line in this 2θ - $\sin^2 \psi$ diagram is equal to the term $\partial(2\theta)/\partial(\sin^2 \psi)$ in Eq. (4).

3 IN-SITU X-RAY THERMAL STRESS MEASUREMENT

In this study, stress alterations caused from low temperature cycling were measured by the in-situ x-ray stress measurement technique. Figure 4 shows photographs of measurement system. W/Ti composite was set on the cooling head of the cryogenic system. The x-ray stress measurement machine MSF-2M (Rigaku Co., Japan) was used in this measurement. This machine has the measurement angle from $2\theta=170^\circ$ to 140° . However, the diffraction peak from the tungsten fiber appears in $2\theta=115^\circ$. Therefore, the extension attachment of the 2θ angel was set on the goniometer of this machine head. The thermo-couple was set on the top surface as well as the x-ray irradiated surface.

Figure 5 shows the schematic diagram of the temperature vs. time program for the in-situ stress measurement of the W/Ti composite. Measurement temperatures are 6 points from 25°C to -250°C at intervals of 50°C . The rate of temperature change is about $5\text{K}/\text{min}$. in the cool down stage and the heat up stage. When the temperature came to a target temperature, it held for about 10 minutes in order to stabilize, and after that the stress measurement started in every case. One cycle consists of the cool down stage and the heat up stage, and three cycles were repeated in this measurement.

Table 2 shows the conditions of the in-situ x-ray stress measurement. Young's modulus: E and Poisson's ratio: ν depending on the hkl diffraction plane were calculated from Kroener model.

Figure 4: X-ray stress measurement system; (a) sample setting and thermocouple on the cooling head. Temperature control was performed by the heater under the sample, (b) x-ray stress measurement system with the 2θ angle extension attachment.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of temperature vs. time program for the in-situ stress measurement of W/Ti composite.

Characteristic x-rays	CrK α
X-ray optics	Parallel beam
Measurement method	2θ - $\sin^2\psi$ and fixed ψ_0 method
Tube voltage [kV] and current [mA]	8, 25
$\sin^2\psi$	0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5
hkl plane & diffraction angle [deg.]	W 211, $2\theta=125.1^\circ$,
2θ step angle [deg.] & fixed time [sec]	W: 0.1° , 10sec.
Filter	Vanadium
Irradiated area [mm]	10 \times 5
Peak deciding method	FWHM method
Young's modulus E , at R.T.	Ti: $E=120.7\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.31$, $\alpha=8.04\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$
Poisson's ratio ν , at R.T.	W: $E=417.7\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.278$, $\alpha=4.43\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$
Coefficient of thermal expansion α , t R.T.	

Table 2: conditions of x-ray stress measurement.

In this measurement, E , ν and thermal expansion coefficient α were considered the temperature dependency [6]. The measurement time for one stress measurement was about 60 minutes for the tungsten fiber. Finally, the measuring time of one cycle in this measurement became about 20 hours.

Furthermore, the simple elastic calculation was performed and compared with experimental results. This calculation assumes the one axial loading model, and it is shown by the following theoretical equation:

$$\sigma_w = \frac{E_w E_{Ti} V_{Ti}}{E_w V_w + E_{Ti} V_{Ti}} (\alpha_w - \alpha_{Ti}) \Delta T$$

$$\sigma_{Ti} = \frac{E_w E_{Ti} V_w}{E_w V_w + E_{Ti} V_{Ti}} (\alpha_w - \alpha_{Ti}) \Delta T, \quad (5)$$

where suffixes mean materials, E is young modulus, α is coefficient thermal expansion, ΔT is temperature difference and V is volume fraction of the tungsten fiber. The Young's modulus E and the thermal expansion coefficient α used the same parameters in Table2, and the volume fraction is $V=0.5\%$ in this calculation. The stress free position which is needed to calculate the residual stresses was supposed on the room temperature 25°C position in both the tungsten fiber and the titanium matrix for convenience.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6 shows the $2\theta\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ diagrams at the typical temperatures in the case of the tungsten fiber. The textile structure was not observed in the tungsten fiber. Therefore, the peak intensity from the tungsten fiber was enough to measure the thermal residual stresses in the every ψ tilt angle. From these results, regression line showed good linearity and diffraction angles shifted to the high angle region with temperature down because of the thermal shrinkage of the lattice spacing in the tungsten fiber. Furthermore, the slope of the regression line increased with the temperature down because thermal residual stresses were generated from the thermal expansion mismatch between the tungsten fiber and the titanium matrix.

Figure 6: $2\theta\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ diagram of several temperatures.

Fig. 7 show results of the in-situ thermal stress measurement in the longitudinal direction stress of the tungsten fiber. The results of the cool down stage and heat up stage are shown by arrow marks in this figure. From these results, the initial residual stress in the tungsten fiber is a compressive state about -810MPa . As the effect of the emery polishing of the sample surface was canceled by the annealing treatment at 630°C for two hours, it is supposed that this compressive residual stress in the tungsten fiber was generated by the thermal expansion mismatch between the tungsten fiber and the titanium matrix. After that, the initial residual stress increased gradually in compressive state with the temperature down under the cool down stage, and it changed to about -980MPa at -250°C . In the next

heat up stage, thermal stresses decreased from -980MPa to -810MPa with the temperature raising. Finally, the thermal residual stresses in the tungsten fiber returned as well as the value of the initial thermal residual stress. However, the cool down stage and the heat up stage go through the different routes, respectively. These routes look like a hysteresis loop.

Figure 7: Result of the neutron in-situ thermal residual stress measurement in tungsten-fiber.

For example, Fig 8 shows results of the in-situ thermal stress measurement by the neutron diffraction cited from the other paper of the same author [7]. These results obtained the same sample in this study. In the neutron stress measurement case, the residual stress in the internal position is estimated as against the x-ray stress measurement estimates on the surface stresses. In Fig.8, three results were shown; (a) results of the transverse direction of the tungsten fiber, (b) results of the longitudinal direction of tungsten fiber, and results of the elastic calculation are plotted in this figure.

Figure 8: Results of the in-situ neutron stress measurement under the cryogenic temperature cycling ;(a) results of the transverse direction of the tungsten fiber, (b) results of the longitudinal direction of tungsten fiber. Results of the elastic calculation are also plotted in this figure. (Masayuki Nishida, Taisei Doi, M. Refai, Tatsuya Matsue, In-situ Stress Measurement of Fiber Reinforced Composite in Low Temperature state by Neutron Diffraction (Second Report), Proceedings of The 48 Symposium on X-RAY Studies on Mechanical Behavior of Materials, The Society of Materials Science, Japan, (2014) pp.103-106.)

From the result of tungsten fiber in Fig.8 (b), the initial residual stress was about 800MPa in the fiber longitudinal direction. This initial residual stress increased gradually with the temperature down under the cool down stage, and it changed to about -1000MPa in 10K(-263°C). In the heat up stage, thermal stresses decreased from -1000MPa to -800MPa with the temperature rise. Furthermore, in the heat up stage and the cool down stage, thermal residual stresses changed through different routes in this measurement. These tendencies of measurement results for the in-situ neutron stress measurement are much as well as the results of the x-ray stress measurement in Fig7. In this result, we would like to attention the residual stress alterations in Fig8 (b): the longitudinal direction results, and compare with the x-ray results. It is clear there were the hysteresis loops in both results. The routs explained the arrow direction in the figure were also same direction. From these results, the hysteresis loop in the thermal cycling process exists without doubt. However, the cause of the hysteresis loop is unknown at this time.

On the other hand, we have already the other measurement technique of the in-situ x-ray stress measurement in the high temperature state. Fig.9 shows the stress alteration from 700°C to -250°C measured by the in-situ x-ray stress measurement technique. Fig9 (a) is equal to the results in Fig.7. And Fig.9 (b) is results cited from the other paper of the same author [5]. This Fig.9 (b) explains the thermal stress alteration from 10°C to 700°C by the in-situ x-ray stress measurement in the high temperature state. (See reference [5] for the detailed explanation). The combination of the x-ray stress measurement technique in the cryogenic region and the high temperature region makes it possible to estimate of the thermal stress estimation in the low-high temperature state.

Figure 9: Combination results of the in-situ x-ray stress measurement technique ;(a) in the cryogenic region, (b) the high temperature region. These combination techniques will make it possible to estimate of the thermal stress estimation in the low-high temperature state.

(MASAYUKI Nishida, MASASHI Haneoka, TATSUYA Matsue, Tian Jing and TAKAO Hanabusa , Thermal Stress Estimation of Tungsten Fiber Reinforced Titanium Composite by In-situ X-ray Diffraction Method, Materials Science Forum Vols. 768-769 (2014) pp 335-342, doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.768-769.335)

5 CONCLUSIONS

- 1) In the initial residual stress of fiber longitudinal direction in the W/Ti composite, the compressive stress existed in the tungsten-fiber.
- 2) Thermal residual stresses in tungsten fiber were changed to other states depending on temperature changes.

3) The combination of the x-ray stress measurement technique in the cryogenic region and the high temperature region makes it possible to estimate of the thermal stresses estimation in the low-high temperature state.

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